

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TEXT TYPES IN TRANSLATION

Khayitboeva Zilola Kurbannazarovna

UrDU, Lingvistika(ingliz tili) yo'nalishi

2-bosqich magistranti

Saparbayeva Gulamdon

Ilmiy maslahatchi, UrDU, PhD

Abstract: *In this article, the elements of the origin of the translation process, the types of texts in translation and their comparative analysis, models, their arrival in the context, and the research and research of translation scientists are mentioned.*

Key words: *translation, text, translation models, types of context, free and literal translation, hidden and open translations, etc.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7579531>

Introduction

Translation and interpreting is one of the oldest creative fields that have been forming in the history and culture of the peoples of the world for centuries. Generations of people who have been living in different continents and regions of the earth for several thousand years have shown their creative passions, interests, opportunities and interests through the medium of translation. He turned it into a means of international communication, which he always used effectively. Through translation and translators, the peoples of mankind became aware of each other and communicated with each other. At the same time, he gradually developed and established industries such as trade, handicrafts, housing, road construction, agriculture, and armaments. People learned from each other how to live a comfortable and safe life, showed each other the way and showed each other the attractive aspects of various cultures.

The context, i.e. the text, is a language phenomenon that prevents the translator from getting lost and choosing the wrong words during the translation process. Literally speaking, the context is the translator's guiding star, beacon. Interrelated meanings of words in the texts are the most reliable tool of the translator.

In linguistics, there are usually two types of context -linguistic and extralinguistic. Linguistic context, in turn, is divided into two types - broad and narrow contexts.[1]

The context in the narrow sense can include a phrase and a sentence, and the context in the broad sense can include a unit larger than a phrase and a whole text. In most cases, the meaning of a word is determined within a small context in the text. Words used in their own sense and words used in a figurative sense have their own characteristics of translation. A translation problem arises when words are not used in the context, i.e. figuratively. In some cases, we need to understand a whole sentence in order to fully understand the meaning of a word. Context is important when choosing words that have multiple meanings.

Take the English word "bus" for example. This word is a shortened form of the word "bus or trolleybus" in the noun sense, and in the verb sense only in America and Canada it has the meaning "to transport my child from one region to another by bus". In addition, this word is used on signs in the student kitchen and has the meaning of "self-service, i.e. take the tray and take it away with the empty dishes after using it."

Sometimes the linguistic context is closely related to extralinguistic factors. It appears when the linguistic context does not fully explain the meaning of the word. For example, one of the characters of Bernard Shaw says: "He warns his interlocutor not to drive him too far, it is necessary to know that they are both sitting in the parlor and not in any vehicle." The English verb "to drive" is used here in the sense of bringing to a situation.

When it comes to neologisms, sometimes the linguistic context can be of no help in deciphering the meaning. A neologism, that is, a new word or phrase, when a new meaning of an old word that is not shown in the dictionary appears, may not have an alternative version of this word in the translated language.

There are also three main models of translation used in translation research. The first is the comparative model, which matches translations with source texts or with parallel (non-translated) texts and examines the relationship between the two. This pattern is evident in contrastive comparative studies.

The second is the process model, which maps the different stages of the translation process over time. This model is represented by communication approaches as well as some protocol approaches. The third is the variable model, in which translations are described both in terms of antecedents and as influenced by readers or listeners and cultures. Also, in world translation studies, four standard (explanatory, descriptive, explanatory and predictive) hypotheses are stated and described based on the phenomenon of retranslation. A single-variable model can fit all four types, and it is the most effective model for future dynamic development in translation studies.

Descriptive hypotheses (such as statements about universals or laws) may have explanatory power, but almost all causal effects are filtered through the mind of the interpreter, through the decisions made by the interpreter at a given moment. Most of the traditional opinions on the typology of translation consist of two opposing directions, "free and literal" translations. A modern interpretation of this distinction was proposed by Newmark (1981) based on semantic and communicative translation.[2]

Semantic translation is closer to literal translation, it gives the most optimal priority to the meaning and form of the original, and is suitable for translations of high-status texts such as religious texts, legal texts, literature, official speeches. Communicative translation is looser and prioritizes the effectiveness of the message being sent. It focuses on factors such as readability and naturalness, and is suitable for translations of "pragmatic" texts that have little to do with the meaning of the original. These include texts such as advertising, travel brochures, product descriptions and instructions, and manuals.

The main problem with this type of differentiation is literalness, proximity or distance, and degrees of freedom. Its single-purpose solution is to analyze and calculate the various changes (shifts, strategies) from text to text.

A slightly different type of translation typology was proposed by Juliane House (1977), covert and overt translations. Hidden translations are not made known to readers about the translators' names. In other words, they translate so naturally (and they are probably very loose translations) that the translated text does not differ much from the original.

Examples of this are advertising, technical texts, newspaper texts. On the other hand, open translations are precise translations, which are closely related to the culture of the sources. Translations of political speeches, poems, and sermons are examples of this. Electronic text studies have shown that hidden translations can contain linguistic features with statistically different distributions compared to untranslated, parallel texts. Therefore, even secret translations may differ in terms of text from the original, and the translated texts may have common features. A similar distinction was made by Nord (1991), who contrasted documentary and instrumental translation.

A documentary translation is a document of a text, which appears as a report of another speech and is like a paraphrase. Instrumental translation, on the other hand, works as a means of communication in itself, it works independently of the original text and is evaluated according to the extent to which it conveys its message. So instrumental translation is a bit like direct speech. For example, the translation of a computer manual is an example, where it is important that the reader understands how to set up and use the computer, and it is not necessary to express the original text as accurately as possible.

It should be mentioned that the typological problem becomes more complicated when text types are introduced. Reisigl and Vermeer (1984) emphasize that the method of translation depends on the specific type of text as well as the purpose of translation. Reiss proposed four main types, the first three of which are very traditional: informational texts, expressive texts, operative (i.e. persuasive, instructive) texts and audio-visual (multi-media) texts. past [5]. Dubbing and subtitling are the main types of audio-visual translation. However, we must be careful not to confuse the classifications of text types with the classifications of translation types, since there are many terminological similarities in the process of text translation. For example, terms such as "Bible translation", "literary translation" or "poetry translation" really refer to text types - that is, the type of text being translated.

Summary

In conclusion, the translation of a particular word begins with its analysis in the context (in the text) and in this translation the relevant and alternative allows you to choose a word. Different contexts can be helpful in revealing the source language, i.e., the original meaning of the word used.

The problem of word choice mainly arises when there is a word in the translated language that is a partial alternative to the word used in the original, and when the alternative word itself does not exist. Translating words that do not have an alternative creates a number of problems. A positive solution to these problems requires a translator to have deep knowledge, skills, and good knowledge of translation models and methods

REFERENCES

1. I.G'afurov, O.Mo'minov, N.Qambarov. TARJIMA NAZARIYASI. «Tafakkur Bo'stoni» Toshkent - 2012
2. Juliane House-Translation as Communication across Languages and Cultures-Routledge (2015) (1) <https://www.academia.edu/38151758/pdf>
3. Азатова, Н. А. Tarjimashunoslikda matn va tarjima turlari masalalari / Н. А. Азатова. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2021 <https://moluch.ru/archive/354/79245/>
4. Nord C. Text analysis in translation: theory, methodology, and didactic application of a model for translation-oriented text analysis. Amsterdam: Rodopi, 1991.
5. Reisigl, M. Rhetoric of Political Speeches. In R.Wodak and V. Koller (Eds), Handbook of Communication in Public Sphere (pp. 243–269). Berlin/New York: Mouton de Gruyter, 2008.

